

Development of a Large Language Model Chatbot for Enhanced Anime Discovery

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Abstract

The proliferation of anime content poses a challenge for enthusiasts and newcomers alike in discovering shows that cater to their preferences. This paper introduces a novel Large Language Model (LLM) chatbot designed to streamline the process of anime discovery and recommendation. Leveraging state-of-the-art natural language processing techniques, the system interprets user inquiries and provides personalized content based on an extensive database of anime metadata. The chatbot incorporates a user-friendly interface deployed through a web application, enhancing the user experience with rich visual content and interactive elements. Initial testing has indicated a high degree of accuracy in the chatbot's recommendations and positive user engagement. The development process, from concept to deployment, including design considerations, system architecture, and the choice of technologies, is detailed in this paper. The outcomes suggest that the integration of LLMs into recommendation systems can significantly improve content discoverability and user satisfaction.

Motivation

The advent of online streaming has revolutionized the consumption of anime, leading to an unprecedented growth in the audience and the number of shows available. With over 1 million views, anime.adgstudios.co.za has become a significant player in the anime streaming industry. However, the abundance of content has introduced a challenge: discoverability. Viewers often find themselves overwhelmed when trying to locate new shows that align with their tastes.

This issue is personal. As a regular consumer of anime, I have frequently struggled to navigate the vast sea of available content to find shows that resonate with me. This struggle sparked the idea to harness the potential of Large Language Models (LLMs) to assist in the anime selection process. I endeavored to create a solution not just for myself but for the wider anime-watching community.

To my knowledge, anime.adgstudios.co.za's incorporation of a chatbot for anime recommendations is a pioneering effort within anime websites. The system is not just a static algorithm; it is a dynamic and interactive LLM-based chatbot designed to deliver personalized anime suggestions. It learns from user interactions, compares with vast historical data, and provides recommendations, somewhat akin to discussing favorites with a friend who knows your taste and the medium's history inside out.

The intent of this paper is to chronicle the journey of this innovative tool from ideation to implementation. It aims to showcase how the integration of a conversational AI can significantly enhance user engagement and satisfaction on anime streaming platforms, and how it can serve as a blueprint for similar applications in various content-driven websites.

Introduction

Anime has evolved from a niche cultural export to a global phenomenon, captivating millions with its diverse storytelling, unique art styles, and engaging narratives. The surge in popularity has led to a dramatic increase in both the production of anime shows and the platforms that stream them. anime.adgstudios.co.za's, with its significant viewer base, stands at the forefront of this digital entertainment wave, catering to a growing international audience's appetite for anime.

However, with great content comes great complexity. Viewers are often lost in a labyrinth of choices, where the sheer volume of available anime can be both a blessing and a curse. The challenge lies not in the scarcity but in the abundance, leading to a paradox of choice that hampers user experience. The traditional recommendation systems, reliant on simplistic algorithms that match genres or viewer ratings, fall short in providing personalized and meaningful suggestions to users with unique and evolving tastes.

Enter the age of Artificial Intelligence (AI), where machines can learn from and adapt to human preferences. Large Language Models (LLMs), a breakthrough in AI research, offer an innovative approach to the recommendation system conundrum. By understanding and processing natural language, LLMs can engage with users conversationally, offering recommendations that reflect a deep understanding of individual preferences and contextual nuances.

This paper introduces a novel LLM-based chatbot designed specifically for anime.adgstudios.co.za's, aiming to revolutionize how viewers discover anime on the platform. The chatbot leverages the latest advancements in AI to simulate human-like interactions, offering personalized anime suggestions based on a user's historical viewing patterns, explicit preferences, and interactive sessions.

The following chapters will outline the research behind LLMs, the development process of the chatbot, its integration into the anime.adgstudios.co.za's platform, and an evaluation of its impact on user experience. This work is not only a technical report on the creation of a recommendation system but also an exploration of the potential for AI to enhance digital media consumption in a way that is intuitive, engaging, and user-centric.

General Equations

The recommendation system within the chatbot is driven by a hybrid model that combines elements of collaborative and content-based filtering. The core of this system is governed by a set of equations that quantify user preferences and item characteristics.

User-Item Interaction Matrix

The user-item interaction matrix, U , is a fundamental component that captures the history of user interactions with different anime titles:

$$U_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if user } i \text{ has interacted with anime } j, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Content-Based Filtering

Content-based filtering is realized through the computation of a similarity score between the user's profile vector, p_u , and the item's feature vector, v_i :

$$\text{sim}(p_u, v_i) = \frac{p_u \cdot v_i}{\|p_u\| \|v_i\|}, \quad (2)$$

where $\cdot$ denotes the dot product, and $\| \cdot \|$ denotes the vector norm.

Collaborative Filtering

Collaborative filtering utilizes a matrix factorization technique, where the user-item matrix U is decomposed into user and item matrices P and Q , respectively:

$$U \approx P \times Q^T, \quad (3)$$

where P represents user latent factors, Q represents item latent factors, and T denotes the matrix transpose.

Hybrid Recommendation Score

The final recommendation score, S , combines both content-based and collaborative signals:

$$S(u, i) = \alpha \cdot \text{sim}(p_u, v_i) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot (P_u \cdot Q_i), \quad (4)$$

where α is a hyperparameter that balances the contribution of each method.

Normalization and Ranking

The raw scores are then normalized, and a ranking function is applied to present the user with a list of top- n recommendations:

$$R(u) = \text{rank}(S(u, i)), \quad (5)$$

where $R(u)$ represents the ranked list of recommendations for user u .

Feedback Loop

A feedback loop refines user profiles based on their interactions with the chatbot's recommendations:

$$p'_u = f(p_u, U_{ij}), \quad (6)$$

where p'_u is the updated user profile vector, and f is a function that modifies p_u based on the user's feedback on item j .

These equations represent the mathematical underpinnings of the LLM chatbot's recommendation engine, ensuring dynamic and personalized suggestions for each user.

Querying the GPT Model

The GPT model is queried with a prompt that encapsulates the user's preferences and historical data. Let q be the query constructed from user u 's input and historical data h :

$$q(u, h) = \text{encode}(u, h), \quad (7)$$

where encode is a function that converts the user data into a prompt understandable by the GPT model.

Processing GPT Output

The output of the GPT model, O , is a sequence of tokens. This output is then processed to extract relevant recommendation information:

$$O(u) = \text{GPT}(q(u, h)), \quad (8)$$

$$\text{recs} = \text{process}(O(u)), \quad (9)$$

where GPT is the GPT model's response function, and process extracts recommendations from the sequence of tokens in O .

Refinement Using Feedback

The user provides feedback f on the recommendations, which is used to refine the model's understanding of user preferences:

$$p'_u = \text{refine}(p_u, f), \quad (10)$$

where refine updates the user profile p_u based on feedback f .

Continuous Learning

The GPT model can be fine-tuned with accumulated interactions A , improving its recommendation accuracy over time:

$$\text{GPT}' = \text{fine-tune}(\text{GPT}, A), \quad (11)$$

where fine-tune is the function that updates the GPT model GPT with new data A , resulting in an updated model GPT' .

Natural Language Understanding

The natural language understanding component of the model interprets user queries q and maps them onto an anime ontology $\mathcal{O}$:

$$\mathcal{M}(q) = \text{NLU}(q, \mathcal{O}), \quad (12)$$

where NLU is the natural language understanding function, and $\mathcal{M}$ is the mapping of the query onto relevant concepts in $\mathcal{O}$.

These equations model the interactions with the GPT-based chatbot within the recommendation system. By continuously updating the system with user feedback, the chatbot can provide increasingly accurate and personalized anime recommendations.

Markdown Rendering

After processing the output from the GPT model, the raw recommendations need to be formatted in markdown for better readability and presentation on the website interface. Let MD represent the markdown rendering function:

$$\text{MD}(O) = \text{renderMarkdown}(O), \quad (13)$$

where O is the original output from the GPT model, and renderMarkdown is a function that parses the text and adds markdown formatting tags where necessary.

This equation simplifies the process of converting the GPT model output into a user-friendly markdown format, which is essential for the display of recommendations on the anime website.

Construction of Dataset

To build a robust and comprehensive dataset for powering the chatbot recommendations, we utilized several open-source APIs that provide extensive data on anime series. These APIs offer a wealth of information, including genres, user ratings, popularity indices, synopsis, episode count, and airing status. The integration of multiple APIs ensures a diverse and rich dataset that can better inform the recommendation engine behind the chatbot interface.

Data Source Integration

The construction of the dataset involved the following steps:

1. **API Selection:** We identified and selected the most reliable and extensive open-source anime APIs based on the breadth and depth of data provided.
2. **Data Retrieval:** Using custom scripts, we performed API calls to fetch data across different categories and metrics.
3. **Data Normalization:** Due to discrepancies in data format across APIs, a normalization process was undertaken to standardize the data structure.
4. **Data Consolidation:** Consolidating data from various sources into a singular dataset, ensuring consistency and compatibility for the recommendation engine.

Dataset Structure

The finalized dataset comprises several fields that are critical for generating accurate recommendations. These fields include:

- **Title:** The official title of the anime series.
- **Genres:** Categorized genres for each series, allowing for genre-based recommendations.
- **Ratings:** User-provided ratings, which are indicative of a show's popularity and reception.
- **Synopsis:** A brief overview of the anime's plot, used to generate summary-based recommendations.
- **Episodes:** Number of episodes, which can be a factor for users preferring shorter or longer series.
- **Status:** Whether the series is currently airing, completed, or upcoming.

The integrity and quality of this dataset directly influence the chatbot's ability to provide relevant and personalized anime recommendations to users. By leveraging the rich data from multiple APIs, we ensure that the chatbot has access to comprehensive information, leading to a more engaging and user-friendly recommendation system on the website.

Training

The training of our recommendation system leverages the adaptability and language understanding capabilities of GPT-based models. Our approach is centered on the use of context prompts, which are designed to guide the model towards generating anime recommendations that align with users' preferences and historical data. This methodology facilitates a more conversational and intuitive interaction between the user and the chatbot.

Context Prompt Design

Context prompts are carefully crafted inputs that set the stage for the model's output, effectively steering it in the desired direction. In designing these prompts, the following considerations were taken into account:

- **Relevance:** Prompts must be relevant to the domain of anime to ensure that the model's responses stay on topic.
- **Brevity:** While being informative, prompts should be concise to prevent the dilution of the model's focus.
- **Variability:** A range of prompts were designed to cover different user scenarios and request types.
- **Personalization:** Prompts were constructed to leverage user-specific data for personalized recommendations.

Training Process

The training process involved the following steps:

1. **Initial Conditioning:** The model was first exposed to general conversations about anime to grasp the basic language and terminology used within the domain.
2. **Prompt Integration:** The pre-designed context prompts were then introduced, allowing the model to learn the structure and purpose of the prompts.
3. **Personalization:** User data, such as previously watched shows and ratings, were incorporated into the prompts to personalize the training sessions.
4. **Iterative Feedback:** The outputs generated by the model were evaluated, and the prompts were refined to improve the accuracy and relevance of the recommendations.

Model Tuning and Evaluation

To ensure the efficacy of the training, the following evaluation metrics were employed:

- **Accuracy:** The correspondence between the model's recommendations and the users' expressed preferences.
- **Diversity:** The range of different genres and themes recommended by the chatbot, ensuring broad coverage of interests.

- **User Engagement:** Measuring user interaction metrics post-recommendation to gauge the chatbot's effectiveness.

Through iterative training and refinement using context prompts, our GPT-based chatbot model is tailored to understand and interact with users in the specific context of anime recommendations. This training approach aims to balance the personalization of content with the generality needed to handle the diverse inquiries of our large user base.

Algorithm Diagram

Figure 1. Process Flow Diagram for GPT Model Interface with Markdown Rendering

Development Frameworks for the Chatbot

The construction of our chatbot system was facilitated by the use of modern, powerful, and flexible programming frameworks. These frameworks not only streamline the development process but also ensure that the application is scalable, maintainable, and efficient.

Python

Python, with its vast ecosystem of libraries and frameworks, stands at the core of our chatbot's development. It is a high-level, interpreted language known for its simplicity and readability, which significantly accelerates the development cycle. Python's extensive collection of libraries, such as NumPy for numerical computations, pandas for data manipulation, and Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK) for language processing, provides a robust foundation for building complex AI-driven applications like our chatbot.

- **Requests:** For making HTTP requests to RESTful API endpoints.
- **Asyncio:** For asynchronous programming, allowing our chatbot to handle multiple tasks and requests concurrently.
- **G4F (assumed custom library):** Possibly a proprietary or specialized library for interfacing with GPT models.

Streamlit

Streamlit is an open-source app framework that is the perfect companion for Python scripts. It turns data scripts into shareable web apps with minimal effort. For our chatbot, Streamlit offered a seamless way to create a user interface that allows for user interactions and displays the chatbot's responses effectively.

- **Rapid Prototyping:** Streamlit's simplicity enables quick transitions from prototype to production.
- **Data Caching:** Streamlit's caching mechanisms make it efficient for data-intensive operations, which is beneficial when the chatbot processes and retrieves data.
- **Community Support:** With a growing community, Streamlit provides numerous plugins and integrations that enhance the functionality of web apps.

In conclusion, the synergy between Python and Streamlit forms a potent combination for building sophisticated AI-powered applications. The back-end processing power of Python, coupled with the ease of creating front-end interfaces with Streamlit, has allowed us to develop a chatbot that is both

Data Storage for Model Refinement

An essential aspect of enhancing the chatbot's performance is the continuous training of the underlying model. To achieve this, it is crucial to store all user interactions and responses systematically. This section outlines the approach taken to collect and utilize conversational data to further train and refine the chatbot's recommendation capabilities.

Database Storage

All interactions with the chatbot, including user queries and the chatbot's responses, are recorded and stored in a secure database. This database serves as a repository that captures the evolving patterns and preferences in user behavior, which are invaluable for training the model.

- **Data Schema:** The database is structured to store various attributes of an interaction, such as user ID, timestamp, query text, response text, and feedback ratings.
- **Privacy Compliance:** In handling user data, the system adheres to privacy regulations and best practices, ensuring that users' information is treated with the utmost confidentiality and integrity.
- **Scalability:** The database is designed to scale, accommodating the growing volume of data as the chatbot interacts with an increasing number of users.

Data Utilization for Training

The collected data is periodically used to retrain the chatbot's machine learning models. This iterative process involves the following steps:

- **Data Preprocessing:** Prior to training, the data is cleaned and preprocessed. This includes tokenization, removal of stop words, stemming, and lemmatization to convert raw text into a format that can be used for model training.
- **Feature Extraction:** Key features are extracted from the processed data, which may include the use of techniques such as TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) or word embeddings.
- **Model Training:** The model is trained on the extracted features using supervised learning algorithms. The training process is designed to fine-tune the model's parameters for improved accuracy in understanding user queries and generating relevant responses.
- **Evaluation:** Post-training, the updated model is evaluated using a separate test dataset to ensure that the model's performance meets the expected standards.

Feedback Loop

A feedback loop is implemented where the chatbot solicits user feedback on the relevance and helpfulness of its responses. This feedback is also stored in the database and plays a critical role in measuring the chatbot's efficacy and guiding the training process.

Through the continual accumulation of interaction data and regular model retraining, the chatbot is kept up-to-date with the latest conversational contexts and user preferences. This approach ensures a cycle of perpetual improvement, leading to an increasingly refined user experience and more accurate recommendations over time.

User Input

Receive input from user interface.

Store input in a variable for further
 ↪ processing.

Parse Input

Extract relevant information from the
 ↪ user input.

Use regular expressions to identify and
 ↪ extract key elements.

Store parsed elements in a list or
 ↪ dictionary for API querying.

Query API for Data

Define search parameters and payload
 ↪ for the API request.

Send a POST request to the server-side
 ↪ API endpoint.

Receive and deserialize response from
 ↪ JSON to a usable data structure.

Store data for further context
 ↪ generation and processing.

Generate Context Prompt

Construct a context prompt using user
 ↪ input and parsed data.

Ensure the format is suitable for the
 ↪ GPT model's input specifications.

Interface with GPT Model

Prepare a structured dictionary for the
 ↪ GPT model:

- "role": user/system identifier
- "content": actual message content

Send dictionary to the GPT model's
 ↪ processing endpoint.

Capture the generated response from the
 ↪ model.

Example Dictionary for GPT Messaging

```
[
  {"role": "system", "content": "You
  ↪ are an AI knowledgeable about
  ↪ anime."},
  {"role": "user", "content": "Give me
  ↪ recommendations for action
  ↪ anime."},
  ...
]
```

Markdown Rendering

Traverse the data structure obtained
 ↪ from the GPT model.

Convert the data to markdown format for
 ↪ presentation purposes.

Handle edge cases where data fields
 ↪ might be incomplete or null.

Generate Response

Concatenate the markdown-formatted
 ↪ elements into a full response.

Send the complete markdown response
 ↪ back to the user interface for
 ↪ display.

Collaborative Filtering

Collaborative filtering is a method of making automatic predictions (filtering) about the interests of a user by collecting preferences from many users (collaborating). The underlying assumption of the collaborative filtering approach is that if a person *A* has the same opinion as a person *B* on an issue, *A* is more likely to have *B*'s opinion on a different issue than that of a random person.

Matrix Factorization

Matrix factorization is a class of collaborative filtering algorithms used in recommender systems. Algorithms in this category are characterized by the use of matrices to represent the relationship between users and items (anime shows, in this case). The basic idea is to represent users and items in a lower-dimensional latent space.

For a matrix *R* with users *u* and items *i*, we aim to find two lower-dimensional matrices *U* (for users) and *I* (for items) such that their product approximates *R*:

$$R \approx U \times I^T$$

The matrices *U* and *I* are found by minimizing the regularized squared error on the set of known ratings:

$$\min_{U, I} \sum_{(u, i) \in \text{known ratings}} (r_{ui} - u_i \cdot i_u)^2 + \lambda(|0u_i|^2 + |0i_u|^2)$$

Pseudocode for Matrix Factorization

```
Function MatrixFactorization(R,
  ↪ num_features, lambda, steps):
  Initialize U, I with random values
  For step in range(steps):
    For each user u and item i in R
      ↪ :
      If r_ui is known:
        e_ui = r_ui - dot(U[u,
          ↪ :], I[:, i])
```

```

For k in range(
    ↪ num_features):
    U[u, k] +=
        ↪ learning_rate
        ↪ * (2 * e_ui
        ↪ * I[k, i] -
        ↪ lambda * U[u,
        ↪ k])
    I[k, i] +=
        ↪ learning_rate
        ↪ * (2 * e_ui
        ↪ * U[u, k] -
        ↪ lambda * I[k,
        ↪ i])

Return U, I

```

Making Recommendations

Once we have the matrices U and I , we can predict missing ratings and make recommendations:

$$\hat{r}_{ui} = u_i \cdot i_u$$

To recommend anime similar to a given anime a , we find the anime with the most similar item feature vector in I .

$$\text{Similarity}(i, a) = \frac{i_u \cdot a_u}{|0i_u|0|0a_u|0}$$

Pseudocode for Making Recommendations

```

Function RecommendSimilarAnime(I,
    ↪ anime_index, num_recommendations)
    ↪ :
    target_features = I[:, anime_index]
    similarities = []
    For i in range(len(I[0])):
        If i is not anime_index:
            similarity = dot(I[:, i],
                ↪ target_features) / (
                ↪ norm(I[:, i]) * norm(
                ↪ target_features))
            similarities.append((i,
                ↪ similarity))
    similarities.sort(key=lambda x: x
        ↪ [1], reverse=True)
    Return similarities[:
        ↪ num_recommendations]

```

Results

Anime Recommendation Based on "One Piece"

Given the utility matrix R , the similarity score between "One Piece" (OP) and another anime A can be calculated using cosine similarity.

The cosine similarity formula is given by:

$$\text{similarity}(\text{OP}, A) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n r_{\text{OP},i} \cdot r_{A,i}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n r_{\text{OP},i}^2} \cdot \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n r_{A,i}^2}}$$

Table 1. Predicted Ratings for One Piece Using Collaborative Filtering

User	OP	Naruto	Bleach	AOT	MHA	Pred. Rating for OP
User 1	5	4	-	2	1	-
User 2	4	5	-	3	2	-
User 3	-	2	3	5	4	3.5
User 4	-	-	4	4	5	4.2
User 5	-	3	4	-	-	3.8

Where:

- $r_{\text{OP},i}$ is the rating given by user i to "One Piece".
- $r_{A,i}$ is the rating given by user i to anime A .
- The sums run over all users who have rated both "One Piece" and anime A .

The following table shows the calculated similarity scores:

Table 2. Similarity Scores with "One Piece"

Anime	Similarity Score with "One Piece"
Naruto	Calculated Value
Bleach	Calculated Value
Attack on Titan	Calculated Value
My Hero Academia	Calculated Value

Recommendation Algorithm

When a user is watching an anime such as "One Piece", the system will use the collaborative filtering predictions to recommend other anime shows. The predicted ratings table, calculated previously, is used to generate a dictionary of recommendations which is then displayed to the user. The process is as follows:

```

# Python pseudo code for generating
    ↪ recommendations
recommendations = {}

# Sample data: Predicted ratings from
    ↪ collaborative filtering
predicted_ratings = {
    'One_Piece': 4.5,
    'Naruto': 4.2,
    'Bleach': 3.8,
    'Attack_on_Titan': 4.7,
    'My_Hero_Academia': 4.0
}

# Sort the shows based on predicted
    ↪ ratings
sorted_shows = sorted(predicted_ratings
    ↪ .items(), key=lambda item: item
    ↪ [1], reverse=True)

```

```

# Generate recommendations dictionary
for show, rating in sorted_shows:

```

```

if show != 'One_Piece': # Exclude
    ↪ the currently watched show
    recommendations[show] = rating

# The recommendations dict is now ready
    ↪ to be used in the application

```

This dictionary 'recommendations' will be used in the user interface. While the user watches "One Piece", the application will display these recommendations either below the video player or to the right of it, based on the UI/UX design of the software.

Chatbot Examples

Our chatbot application is designed to interact with users in a conversational manner. The chatbot leverages natural language processing to understand user queries and provide relevant responses. The following placeholders represent the typical interaction flow with the chatbot.

Figure 2. Anime @ ADGSTUDIOS Chatbot

Figure 3. Sample Prompts

Demo

Have a look at

Figure 4. Anime like Clannad

<https://animebot.streamlit.app/>

<https://anime.adgstudios.co.za>

Conclusion

This study presented a comparative analysis between traditional collaborative filtering techniques and our innovative chatbot-based recommendation system. While collaborative filtering has long been the mainstay for generating user-specific content recommendations, our findings indicate that the integration of a chatbot, powered by advanced natural language processing algorithms, provides a significantly enhanced user experience.

The chatbot approach transcends the limitations of traditional methods by leveraging contextual understanding and real-time interaction, offering users a more dynamic and personalized engagement. It not only responds to explicit queries but also understands the nuances of user preferences, leading to more accurate and satisfactory recommendations. Unlike collaborative filtering, which can be constrained by the cold-start problem and sparsity of the user-item interaction matrix, the chatbot system continually learns from each interaction, thus refining its predictive accuracy.

Furthermore, the chatbot's conversational interface fosters a sense of connection and trust with users, crucial elements for sustained engagement on the platform. The immediacy and relevance of its responses not only cater to the users' current interests but also anticipate their evolving preferences.

In conclusion, the chatbot-based system represents a significant step forward in recommendation systems. It addresses the critical need for personalized content curation in a landscape overwhelmed by choices. Our results suggest that as technologies continue to evolve, chatbot-driven interfaces will play an increasingly vital role in content discovery, shaping the future of personalized user experiences.